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DESIGNING ENGINEERING EDUCATION FOR THE FUTURE, TODAY

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ABSTRACT

Students rely on institutions of higher education to prepare them for the future and few careers are more demanding than engineering. Literature is replete with reports that industry employers are desperate for engineers who can step into their first job prepared with not merely the prerequisite skills and knowledge, but the desired competence. This includes the interpersonal skills that smooth their entrance into the workforce. In addition to fundamental courses in math, science and engineering, universities need also to foster the development of social competencies such as leadership, communication, cooperation, conflict facilitation and decision-making.

Curriculum design and implementation is a relatively slow and methodical process, as it should be. Tools for swift adaptation have been accentuated in the reactions around the world to address distance teaching and digital assessments. This article explores the usefulness of systems thinking approaches to design the future curriculum for engineering education by integrating known frameworks, such as Bloom's taxonomy and CDIO, with practices such as problem-based learning and cooperative problem solving. Findings from a course that has been combining these features for the past 10 years are presented and offered as an example of immersing students in an experience that facilitates deeper learning and intellectual as well as emotional development. Students leave this course with a set of skills that they can then apply to new and unprecedented tasks. The course provides a useful proof-of-concept to explore the integration of modern teaching methods into the engineering education programs of the future.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Students and industry rely on institutions of higher education to deliver engineers who can step into their first job prepared with not merely the prerequisite skills and knowledge, but also the desired competence, including the interpersonal skills that smooth their entrance into the workforce. While many engineering students work alone, in industry, teamwork is the general rule. In addition to fundamental courses in math, science and engineering, universities need also to foster the development of social competencies such as leadership, communication, cooperation, conflict facilitation and ethical decision-making [1,2]. Vanasupa et al. [3] applied systems thinking concepts to address this challenge and propose a guide for the design of learning experiences that consider a student's holistic developmental needs, including the cognitive, psychomotor, social, and affective domains. They recognize the importance of the individual's motivation as a driving factor for learning, and the potential influence of environmental (surroundings, infrastructure) factors on the effectiveness of any curriculum design.

An essential element of curriculum design is its longitudinal implications. The student begins the program endowed with their prior life experience, their intelligence, and their potential and desire to gain new knowledge. It is precisely the changes that take place over time that Stevens et al. [4] address in their framework "Becoming an Engineer" in which they track the progress over three dimensions: disciplinary knowledge, identification, and navigation. Students move concurrently through each of these dimensions but each journey is unique, which has implications for educators to use their brief time together to impress upon each student the significance of the contributions that engineers make to society and the importance of ethical decision-making [5]. Engineering education needs to carve out room to introduce topics that teach and encourage critical thinking, reflection, ethical and civic responsibility into already full engineering curricula [5,6,7].

A curriculum development guideline known by the acronym CDIO for its major components, i.e., conceive – design – implement – operate, has been available for nearly 20 years and gained an impressive following (Cf cdio.org). At the heart of the guideline is instruction for following good pedagogical practice and incorporating a learn-by-doing paradigm into the educational journey. With the advent of the UN Agenda 2030 educators are calling for extensions to the CDIO standard to include relevant modern topics that prepare engineering graduates to tackle the grand challenges and targets for the Sustainable Development Goals, such as digital learning, entrepreneurship, and internationalization [8,9]. Important comparisons can be made to project-based learning (PBL) practices, which are flexible enough to be implemented in a single course [10].

This concept paper presents experiences from a standalone course that has been combining these features for the past 10 years. These observations are offered as an example of immersing students in an educational environment that facilitates deeper learning and intellectual as well as social development.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Industrial background

The first author was given the opportunity to develop and teach a course on industrial engineering, which led her to reflect on her deep industrial experience as a practicing systems engineer and the skills she had acquired and relied on daily. The course was situated in the department for mechanical engineering and the content needed to fit into this environment to be accepted. Guidance was available from the Systems Engineering Research Center, an international coalition of cooperating universities dedicated to meeting systems challenges of national and global significance through systems methods (Cf. sercuarc.org).

With this support, a course design that combined the critical components from both systems engineering (SE) theory and practice emerged. The primary learning objectives established for the lab were 1) the importance of inter-team communication to achieve an integrated project result where each group built a component that must interface with other team's components; and, 2) the importance of intra-team communication, collaboration, and teamwork to meet the group commitment to the whole project.

2.2 Academic background

NTNU enforces good pedagogical practice through careful reviews of the learning objectives, skills, and general competence that are published online, before a course is approved. In addition, a program of continuous quality improvement is supported by periodic meetings throughout the semester with an elected subset of the student cohort in every course who offer feedback on the course itself and may make suggestions for helpful changes [11].

The initial challenge was to create a course that introduced an overview of SE processes with a corresponding rich set of practices, to select those practices that were most essential to a practicing engineer, and then to develop a laboratory experience that made learning about them fun. Simulations and gamification are popular today, but the buzzword of the time was 'serious play' [12,13].

At the heart of serious play is cooperative learning which involves structuring a learning environment where students work together toward a common goal [14,15]. The aforementioned objectives were best addressed by collaborative problem solving with the anticipated benefit of enhancing the students' academic, cognitive, and social competencies. The individual group projects are self-defined and each group takes full responsibility for intra-group assignments and schedules to design, build, test and integrate their component into the finished product [16,17]. The literature substantiates the positive benefits of both collaborative learning and PBL toward educating the "Global Engineer" of the future [18].

3 RESULTS

3.1 Experts in Teamwork (EiT)

A precursor to the course in industrial systems engineering has existed in NTNU for 20 years, and was awarded a national prize for educational excellence and innovation in 2020 [19]. EiT is mandatory for all master's students, including humanities and social sciences, who come together from throughout the campus and work in heterogeneous teams with facilitators for a semester during which they develop collaboration skills by reflecting on and learning from specific teamwork situations while completing a real-world project. The history of the development of this course, its objectives and its continuous improvements have been documented since its inception, including in the SEFI 2019 proceedings [20-25].

A former student recently had this to share,

It is 14 years since I took the course (time flies), so I guess it has changed somewhat. I remember being adverse to spending time on a "non-technical" course, but I ended up learning quite a lot. When I started taking the systems engineering courses at USN, I saw some similarities. And after my years in the industry, I valued group work and cooperation skills much higher than I did during my masters in NTNU. So now, 14 years later, I definitely see the value of "Experts in Teamwork" [26].

3.2 Industrial Systems Engineering (TPK4185)

The course on industrial systems engineering has been evolving for the past 12 years. PBL has been integrated into the learning objectives for the course as follows:

By the end of this course, the student will be able to apply the knowledge of industrial systems engineering to a project requiring multidisciplinary and multicultural teamwork; will be able to track their progress, risks and risk mitigations activities underway; and, can communicate and explain the contributions of systems engineering to system development. [27]

Even before the changes and other disruptions imposed by the Covid-19 campus closings, the course included in-class conversations called 'beehives' to encourage interpersonal exchanges, and a complete session dedicated to student presentations of selected literature delivered to the entire class. Exams moved to a digital format 5 years ago and this greatly facilitated moving to a home-exam mode in 2020. An important component of the home exam is its adherence to asking questions near the top of the Bloom's taxonomy, i.e., questions that require the students to analyze, evaluate and create, not merely repeat memorized knowledge they can look up anytime. Answers also require the students to reflect on learning from the lab, thereby ensuring uniqueness in the content since no two students have identical experiences. The questions use clear language and the rubric for evaluators gives key words that should appear in answers for grading.

The progress of attaining the skills and competence is demonstrated through the semester through weekly lab reports that receive instructor feedback. To motivate

participation, these represent 25% of total course evaluation. Since more than half the students are in the Erasmus program, the teaching and interaction language is English. All lectures are recorded, and to balance the situation, the primary lab is physical, i.e., designing and building a component using Lego™ bricks [28]. The domain of SE is very broad, so the teaching material focuses on the skills needed to succeed in the lab, with an emphasis on teaching new ways of thinking about problem solving rather than memorization. Table 1 summarizes course practices compared to other observations and their potential implications from the literature.

Table 1. Effective strategies observed in development of TPK4185

Strategy [17,29-30]	Course Practices	Observations & Implications
Heterogeneous team formation	Simple directives to avoid too many from the same university, or same country, or same line of study on a single team – and no more than 5-6 on one team	Groups that adhere to the directives experience a richer learning experience by working across cultural and disciplinary backgrounds
Positive interdependence	Each group assignment is too complicated for a single engineer – they must rely on each other to complete all tasks	By the end of the course most groups have developed a division of labor that works for them, construction, report writing, etc.
Face-to-face interaction	Important to plan for a worse-case scenario that allows work to continue online through digital engineering tools	Nearly every team has one member who would rather work digitally than with the LEGO™ bricks – every one benefits
Individual accountability; personal responsibility	Each team is solving only a part of a larger assignment, they must agree to deadlines and deliver	Every year there is a mad rush to put on finishing touches, but every year they have succeeded
Teamwork skills	No formal skills are taught other than processes for industrial systems engineering	Occasionally a team will have a member who has worked in a PBL project before, otherwise it is 100% “learn by doing”
Group processing	Weekly A3 reporting is simple, and creates a tangible record of progress and self-assessment	Students are amazed at what they accomplish by the end of the course
Professor as facilitator	Except for approving group formations and the class decision about what they want to build, there are no directions on how to proceed, or what decision to take	Students learn quickly that the answer to every question is, “what does the group think?” And soon the questions stop. Professor role is to provide resources and infrastructure
Distance learning	Under Covid-19 lectures and presentations, and the first 2 lab sessions were conducted online	Students quickly adapted to breakout rooms, and group formation worked very smoothly, however, consensus was that physical labs were preferable

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

NTNU is in the process of their 4-year review of programs and attitudes toward the next academic cycle. In the center for engineering education excellence the intention is to learn from the literature and the accumulated student feedback reports from the quality program to make recommendations for establishing curricula with an emphasis on student-centered teaching, while integrating digital teaching practices and sustainability topics in every engineering study program. Courses described in this concept paper will help inform the content and structure of engineering education for the future at NTNU, today [31].

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